

UPDATED DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (year 2)

Deliverable 1.5

Updated data management plan (year 2)

HIGH HORIZONS – D1.5

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Version 1.2	Corrections and updates made on version 1.1 (17 June 2024)
Version 1.3	New structure added to the document to reflect intermediate reporting towards a final DMP (18 July 2024)
Version 2.0	Internally revised and approved version (28 August 2024)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
AKDN	Aga Khan Development Network
AKHS	Aga Khan Health Services (Kenya)
BELNET	Belgian National Research & Education Network
CARBOMICA	Resource optimisation tool for CARBOn Mitigation Interventions in healthCare facilities
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CSV	Comma-separated values
DG	Data generation
DMP	Data management plan
DOI	Digital object identifier
DR	Data reuse
DTU	Technical University of Denmark (Denmark)
ERA5	The 5th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
EU	European Union
EWS	Early warning system
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (data)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance System
IP	Intellectual Property
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
POPIA	Protection of Personal Information Act (South Africa)
RDM	Research data management
SC	Steering Committee
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (The Netherlands)
UGent	Ghent University (Belgium)
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UK	United Kingdom
ULUND	Lund University (Sweden)
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
UTH	University of Thessaly (Greece)
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
WHO	World Health Organisation
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)
WOMBAT	Work Observation Method by Activity Timing
WP	Work Package

1 Background

1.1 Data management plan updates

HIGH Horizons is committed to apply the Open Science principles, both in the context of scholarly publishing, i.e. open access to publications and open peer review, and with respect to research data management (RDM), i.e. the generation of findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR) data.

At the start of the HIGH Horizons project, we wrote a publication policy¹, which was since expanded with standard operating procedures and the establishment of a Publication Committee. We also developed the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), initially written in [DMPonline](#), an online tool that guides its users through the DMP template of the funding agency and that is hosted at BELNET which holds/stores the data management plans on behalf of the client (i.c. Ghent University) on secure servers in Belgium. The resulting online DMP was downloaded as a Word document and submitted as deliverable 1.4 in November 2022 (1).

This first update builds on the original version of our DMP, but we have restructured the document to reflect intermediate reporting towards a final DMP (2, 3).

1.2 Data management procedures

With Ghent University coordinating the HIGH Horizons project, we apply the Ghent University's policy framework on Research Data Management (4) as good as possible. While our European partners are familiar with the EU's policy on open science, our African partners (i.c. AKHS Kenya, Wits RHI and CeSHHAR) also need to comply with national procedures for data protection and management, including the Data Protection Act 2019 of Kenya (5), the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) of South Africa (6), and the Data Protection Act 2021 of Zimbabwe (7).

¹ Project deliverable 1.3 is available on the CORDIS website ([Projects & results | CORDIS | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)).

World Health Organisation complies with its personal data protection framework, which includes the WHO Personal Data Protection Policy and the UN Personal Data Protection and Privacy Principles (8).

1.3 Data management support

For the HIGH Horizons data management plan, we are supported by the research data management team at Ghent University (the project's coordinating organisation) and by partner leads and data stewards from consortium partners for additional guidance.

In August 2024, the following persons are supporting and responsible for the HIGH Horizons research data management:

- In Belgium:
 - Project coordinator: Stanley Luchters² – Ghent University & CeSHHAR
 - Project manager (including RDM): Birgit Kerstens – Ghent University
- In Austria:
 - Partner lead: Ilona Otto – University of Graz
 - Data manager & researcher: Chloe Brimicombe – University of Graz
- In Denmark:
 - Project lead & data manager: Jørn Toftum – Technical University of Denmark
- In Greece:
 - Project lead: Barbara Mouchtouri – University of Thessaly
 - Data manager & researcher: Michalis Koureas, Evangelos Kokkalis – University of Thessaly
- In Sweden:
 - Partner lead & data manager (primarily for data related to the testing and evaluation of the early warning system): Chuansi Gao – Lund University
 - Partner lead & data manager (primarily for Swedish pregnancy register and health-related data generated in HIGH Horizons studies): Olof Stephansson – Karolinska Institutet

² The HIGH Horizons project coordinator is also one of the two internal ethics advisors of the project.

- In the United Kingdom:
 - Deputy project coordinator, partner lead & data manager: Debra Jackson – London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
- In Kenya:
 - Partner lead: Sohail Baloch – Aga Khan Health Services, Kenya
 - Data Manager: James Siku – Aga Khan Health Services, Kenya
- In South Africa:
 - Partner lead: Gloria Maimela – Wits RHI
 - Data manager: Jean Le Roux – Wits RHI
- In Zimbabwe:
 - Partner lead: Fortunate Machingura – CeSHHAR
 - Data manager: Jeffrey Dirawo – CeSHHAR

The roles and responsibilities for research data management after the end of HIGH Horizons will be described in the next update in August 2025. The Steering Committee (SC) has discussed the establishment of a Data Access Committee and decided that the SC itself can assume the responsibility of granting data access, and will reassess this decision by the end of the HIGH Horizons project.

1.4 Data utility

The HIGH Horizons project addresses key knowledge gaps around the quantification and monitoring of direct and indirect impacts of heat exposure on maternal, newborn and child health, by focusing on the following objectives:

- (1) **Indicators:** Using systematic reviews, data (re)analyses of heat impacts on maternal, newborn and child health outcomes, and data science predictive modelling on maternal and newborn health data from several countries including Greece, Italy, Sweden, Kenya and South Africa, we will increase our understanding of the relationships between heat and maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) outcomes and we inform the selection and tracking of global, European and national indicators, as well as cut-off thresholds for the Early Warning System (EWS).
- (2) **Early Warning System:** Through a smartphone app, ClimApp-MCH (based on the existing ClimApp, and MCH referring to maternal and child health), the EWS delivers

notifications and context-specific messages, co-designed locally. ClimApp-MCH will be evaluated for its usability, acceptability and effectiveness, among 60 health workers and 600 mothers and infants in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

- (3) **Adaptation and mitigation interventions:** We aim to identify cost-effective adaptation-mitigation interventions. The design of adaptation interventions will be informed by the assessment of environmental and thermal exposures in health facilities in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe and by the health worker baseline assessments both cold and hot seasons in the same countries. The design of mitigation interventions will be based on carbon emission assessments conducted through the Aga Khan Development Network (AKDN) carbon management tool in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe and a resource allocation tool for carbon emission mitigation interventions in health facilities, CARBOMICA, developed by HIGH Horizons.
- (4) **Policy:** Throughout the project, HIGH Horizons will engage relevant stakeholders, prioritising country partners, European Union, African and global policy makers.
- (5) **Biomarkers**³: Specific biomarkers will be measured among pregnant women and their infants in a prospective mother-child birth cohort in Greece and Cyprus to better understand the role of heat exposure on adverse health outcomes. Urine-specific gravity will be assessed as a heat-specific biomarker among participants in Zimbabwe and South Africa.

HIGH Horizons applies an interdisciplinary approach to achieve its five specific objectives by including biomedical and climate science, geospatial analysis, health systems thinking, health economics, and social and behavioural science. For this purpose, a wealth of data(sets) is reused and generated.

The HIGH Horizons work packages are centred around baseline assessment (WP2), design (WP3), implementation (WP4) and evaluation (WP5).

³ This objective was added to the HIGH Horizons project in April 2023 when University of Thessaly (Greece) joined the consortium thanks to the Horizon Europe Hop On grant.

Our data can be useful for researchers in the fields of climate change and heat; maternal, newborn and child health; implementation science; indicator development; EWS development; epidemiology, social sciences and health economics; and for policymakers working on impact of climate change on health.

2 Research data summary & description

Both data reuse and data generation will support the HIGH Horizons studies.

Data reuse (DR). Existing de-identified data will be reused and (re)analysed, mainly for assessing the impact of heat exposures on maternal, newborn and child health.

Examples of reuse of secondary and deidentified data(sets) are:

Databases of environmental factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, air pollution and vegetation index): ERA5⁴;

- Maternal, newborn and child health outcomes at health facility, regional or country level:
 - Greece: nationwide birth register
 - Italy: regional Lazio Certificate of Delivery Care Registry
 - Kenya: routine electronic medical records in health facilities run by Aga Khan Health Services (AKHS) in Mombasa
 - South Africa: electronic system data from one health district (Tshwane) and one sub-district in Johannesburg (Region F)
 - Sweden: nationwide population register consisting of all MNCH health outcomes from 2014 onwards
 - Sub-Saharan Africa: consolidated data from the INDEPTH network and the Health and Demographic Surveillance System (HDSS), from 29 sites from

⁴ ERA5 is a state-of-the-art dataset that provides global gridded data every 1 hour at a 0.25x0.25° grid scale, providing data for regions where observations are sparse. ERA5 is the only product available open source that provides data for Mean Radiant Temperature and the thermal comfort index the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) as part of ERA5-HEAT. Mean Radiant Temperature is required to calculate Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT), an international standard for heat stress. Both, the UTCI and WBGT are thermal comfort indices of interest in HIGH Horizons.

across sub-Saharan Africa from 13 countries (The Gambia, Senegal, Ghana, Burkina Faso, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Malawi, Mozambique and South Africa); data were collected through surveys taking place every month, from 1990 until 2019.

Data generation (DG). Data will be generated in the countries where mitigation and adaptation interventions in health facilities will be implemented and evaluated, or where findings from data analyses help to inform these interventions, such as the health worker study to assess the well-being and productivity of health workers when exposed to heat or the application of the Aga Khan Development Network (AKDN) carbon management tool to measure the carbon emissions in selected health facilities. New data will also be generated in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe through testing and evaluating the EWS ClimApp-MCH. Table 1 gives an overview of the data reuse and generation in each of the study countries of HIGH Horizons.

Table 1: Overview of data reuse and/or generation by country

Country	DATA REUSE	MAINLY DATA GENERATION			
	Data analysis for assessment of heat-health impacts (WP2)	EWS for Pregnant Women & Health Workers (WPs 3, 4 & 5)	Facility Adaptation* (WPs 2, 3, 4, 5)	Facility Mitigation** (WPs 2, 3, 4, 5)	Biomarker analysis (WP2)
Greece [^]	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Italy	Yes	No	No	No	No
Kenya	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
South Africa	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes [°]
Sweden	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes [°]
Zimbabwe	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes [°]

* Facility Adaptation is to reduce heat/temperature in the facilities, e.g., fans, air conditioners.

** Facility Mitigation is to reduce greenhouse gases from facilities, e.g., solar panels, reducing emissions from waste.

[^] The mother-child cohort in Greece is planned to be expanded with recruitment in Nicosia, Cyprus. Ethics approval is pending (August 2024).

[°] With the addition of the biomarker study in Greece, we plan to test 1-2 dehydration biomarkers in the cohorts recruited in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe to evaluate the EWS ClimApp-MCH.

For more details about which data we (will) use or generate and how, we refer to the respective reports/deliverables in Table 2.

Table 2: HIGH Horizons deliverables with data management aspects

Number	Deliverable title*	Data reuse / generation
WP2: Assessment		
D2.1	Environmental-health databases 1 (9)	DR & DG
D2.3	Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 1 (10)	DR & DG
D2.6	Updated systematic review 1**	DR
D2.8	Environmental exposures in health facilities (11)	DR & DG
D2.10	Health workers impact baseline analysis°	DR & DG
D2.11	Carbon emission assessment (12)	DR & DG
D2.12	Study initiation package (13)	DG
WP3: Design & selection		
D3.1	Expert Group established and operational (14)	DR
D3.2	Methods for selection of indicators°°	DR
D3.3	Report on predictive heat warning thresholds (15)	DR
D3.4	ClimApp-MCH prototype: An early warning system app for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and young children, and health workers (16)	DR & DG
D3.5	Report on photo voice sub-study, and the locally-adapted and optimized messaging (17)	DG
D3.6	Report on selection of alternative adaptation interventions^	DG
D3.7	Tool for modelling of alternative mitigation interventions (18)	DR & DG
WP4: Implementation		
	No deliverables yet	
WP5: Evaluation		
D5.2	Protocol for testing of the EWS among pregnant and postpartum women, and young children (19)	DG
D5.7	Protocol and ethics approval for mitigation interventions evaluation (20)	DG

Notes: * When the project deliverable is approved by the EU, we deposit it in the EU Open Research Repository in Zenodo, so that we have a persistent identifier (see also chapter 4.1) ** Under embargo until peer-reviewed publication available. ° Not yet approved by the EU because some country findings are missing. °° Not yet approved by the EU because the final list of indicators is expected. See report of the first scoping meeting of the WHO Expert Group in (13). ^ Not deposited because changes were made to the methodology to select adaptation interventions.

Tables 3 and 4 show the reused data and generated data, and their data management characteristics. In the last column, we refer to the connected project deliverable that describes the dataset and analysis results, and which are listed in table 2. When the dataset is final, we highlight the row to show that these details are complete. We estimate that HIGH Horizons will generate and reuse data with a size of at least 20 TB⁵.

⁵ The dataset with environmental factors, with calculations of heat indices such as UHCI and WBGT, has a size of approximately 20 TB.

2.1 Reuse of secondary and de-identified data and other research outputs (DR)

Table 3: Data reuse by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation											
DR 2.1	Database of environmental factors and heat indices	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	netcdf (.nc)	Raw, processed and published data	No	No	20TB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.1 & D2.3
DR 2.2	Database of nation-wide Greek birth register data	Numerical & Qualitative data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	312MB	No	Approval for UTH ⁶	D2.3
DR 2.3	Database with time series of human thermal stress indices in Greece, aggregated at commune level	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	No	No	1.85GB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.3
DR 2.4	Database of Italian birth register data for Lazio region 2001-2019	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	SAS7B DAT	Processed data	Yes	No	700 MB	No	Approval for ASL Roma (subcontract)	D2.1 & D2.3
DR 2.5	Database of nation-wide Swedish birth register data	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	1.26 GB	No	Approval for KI	D2.1 & D2.3
DR 2.6	Database of MNCH outcomes in health facilities in Kenya	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed data	Yes	No	25KB	No	Data sharing agreement for UGRAZ ⁷	D2.1 & D2.3
DR 2.7	Database of MNCH outcomes in health facilities in South Africa	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	Yes	No	37GB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI ⁸	D2.1 & D2.3

⁶ Ethics application approved by UTH Ethics Committee on 31 July 2023.

⁷ Data sharing agreement signed by Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa and University of Graz on 11 October 2023. UGRAZ is responsible for the data analysis.

⁸ LSHTM also has ethics approval to conduct secondary analyses of two birth register datasets from the Gauteng Tshwane health district of South Africa. Both datasets had been shared before with LSHTM for secondary analyses within the CHAMNHA (Climate, Heat, and Maternal and Neonatal Health in Africa) project and LSHTM wanted to extend (not duplicate) the analyses already undertaken within CHAMNHA for the purposes of HIGH Horizons.

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
DR 2.8	Database with HDSS child health data	Numerical data	Derived from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	1GB	Yes	[open health data from INDEPTH ⁹]	D2.3
DR 2.9	Database of selected MNCH outcomes registered in Austria	Numerical data	Derived from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Processed and published data	No	No	20KB	No	Data sharing agreement with UGRAZ	D2.3 & D2.4
Note	<i>Initially the plan was to establish a merged database with all the above environmental and health data, but because of restricted data sharing of the health datasets, we have merged the environmental and health data per country (each time DR2.1 with DR2.2 to DR2.9) for data analysis purposes.</i>										
DR 2.10	Summary table of all studies on association between high temperatures and MNCH outcomes & included in the updated systematic literature review	Numerical & textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Published data	No	No	10MB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.6
DR 2.11	Spreadsheet with indoor and outdoor temperatures and outdoor weather at the sites	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv) DMY	Raw, processed and published data	No	No	200MB	Yes	Not applicable	D2.8
DR 2.12	Spreadsheet with climate and health terms, their definitions and sources	Textual data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Published data	No	No	93KB	Yes, on GitHub	Not applicable	See (22)
DR 2.13	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical Data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	2MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DR 2.14	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical Data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	2MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DR 2.15	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (baseline) in Sweden	Numerical Data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	No DR yet	No	Ethics approval pending	D2.10

⁹ [INDEPTH Network | Better Health Information for Better Health Policy \(indepth-network.org\)](https://www.indepth-network.org/)

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal/ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions											
DR 3.1	Algorithms/scripts from the original ClimApp software application	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking	Cordova code	App code	No	No	8.5MB (iOS)	Yes, on GitHub	IP agreement with TNO (subcontract)	D3.4
DR 3.2	API to retrieve the local weather conditions from OpenWeatherMap for alerts in ClimApp-MCH	Numerical weather data	Compiled from other (open) sources	.JSON, .XML, and .HTML	Published data	No	No	No DR yet	Yes	Not applicable	D3.4
WP4 - Implement monitoring mechanisms, Early Warning Systems, and adaptation and mitigation interventions in health facilities											
Note	No datasets yet										
WP5 - Evaluate the surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions, including cost-effectiveness											
DR 5.1	Database with routine data about health services and human resources (endline) in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	No DR yet	No	Ethics applications in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe pending	D5.6
DR 5.2	Spreadsheet with cost and financial data from health facilities	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	CSV (.csv)	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DR yet	No	Ethics applications in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe pending	D5.6

2.2 Generation of primary data and other research outputs (DG)

Table 4: Data generation by HIGH Horizons

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
WP2 - Assessment of heat-health impacts and gaps in health facility adaptation and mitigation											
DG 2.1	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo) CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	9MB	Yes, once all measurements done	Not applicable	D2.8
DG 2.2	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in Sweden	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo) CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	4MB	Yes, once all measurements done	Not applicable	D2.8
DG 2.3	Spreadsheet with indoor temperature and air humidity in selected health facilities in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	HOBO (.hobo) CSV (.csv)	Raw data	No	No	8MB	Yes, once all measurements done	Not applicable	D2.8
DG 2.4	Database of MNCH outcomes and other variables for priority setting within HIGH Horizons	Textual data	Derived from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Process and published data	No	No	0.05MB	Not yet	Not applicable	D2.1 & D2.3
DG 2.5	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in Kenya	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	13.5MB	Yes, upon publication	Not applicable	D2.11

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 2.6	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in South Africa	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	12.5GB	Yes, once validation completed	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.11
DG 2.7	Spreadsheet with carbon emission measurements in health facilities in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Derived/compiled from other sources	XLS (.xls)	Raw and processed data	No	No	80MB	Yes, once validation completed	Not applicable	D2.11
Note	<i>The carbon emission data (DG2.5 to DG2.7) have not been merged into one dataset because the data are reused per country to assess the optimal resource allocation for carbon footprint mitigation interventions in selected health facilities in each of the countries.</i>										
DG 2.8	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical & string data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	16MB	Yes (after publication)	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.9	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical & string data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	16MB	Yes (after publication)	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.10	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted in health facilities (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical & string data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	16MB	Yes (after publication)	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.11	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted in health facilities (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	6MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 2.12	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (baseline) in South Africa	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	1GB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.13	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG2.12	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp).txt	Processed data	Yes	No	100MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.14	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	5.17GB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.15	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG2.14	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp).txt	Processed data	Yes	No	700MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.16	Dataset about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline), in South Africa	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	5MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.17	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline) in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	26KB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.14
DG 2.18	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline) in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	26KB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.14
DG 2.19	Dataset about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline), in Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	356KB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.20	Dataset of FitBit observations in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	40MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 2.21	Dataset of FitBit observations in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	38MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.22	Dataset of core body sensors data/observations in South Africa	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	35MB	No	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D2.10
DG 2.23	Dataset of core body sensors data/observations in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	35MB	No	Ethics approval for CeSHHAR	D2.10
DG 2.24	Algorithms/scripts of the heat-health data analyses	Numerical data	Simulation data	.R, .ipynb and .py	Processed data (see DR table)	No	No	33KB	Yes (in D2.3)	Not applicable	D2.3
DG 2.25	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (baseline) in Sweden	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval for KI pending	D2.10
DG 2.26	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of the work environment and activities conducted in health facilities (baseline) in Sweden	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval for KI pending	D2.10
DG 2.27	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (baseline) in Sweden	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval for KI pending	D2.10
DG 2.28	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG2.23	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp) .txt	Processed data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval for KI pending	D2.10
DG 2.29	Dataset about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, and how the health workers feel, administered by the health workers themselves (baseline), in Sweden	Numerical & textual data	Survey	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval for KI pending	D2.10

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 2.30	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (baseline) in Sweden	Numerical Data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Ethics approval pending for KI	D2.14
DG 2.31	Predictive and attributive modelling , applying data science methods	Numerical & categorical data	Data science methods	x	Raw, processed and published data	Yes	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable (ethics approvals and data sharing agreements available from DR above)	D2.5
DG 2.32	Mother-child cohort database , including biomarker measurements, questionnaire data, clinical examination records, birth outcomes, exposure data, and additional relevant information	Numerical and textual data	Observational	MySQL database in Red-Cap; exportation to various formats	Raw data	Yes	No	On-going data collection	No	Ethics approval for UTH	D2.14
WP3 - Design surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions											
DG 3.1	Images from the Photovoice sub-study in South Africa	Visual data	Observational	JPEG (.jpeg)	Raw data	Yes	Yes	137M B	Yes	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG 3.2	Images from the Photovoice sub-study in Zimbabwe	Visual data	Observational	JPEG (.jpeg)	Raw data	No	No	544M B	Yes	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CesHHAR	D3.5
DG 3.3	Audio recordings of Photovoice workshops with pregnant/postpartum women and FGDs with health workers in the development of messages in South Africa	Audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	1.5GB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 3.4	Transcripts based on audio recordings from messaging development in South Africa	Textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw and processed data	No	No	100MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG 3.5	Audio recordings of Photovoice workshops with pregnant/postpartum women and FGDs with health workers in the development of messages in Zimbabwe	Audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	163MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CesHHAR	D3.5
DG 3.6	Transcripts based on audio recordings from messaging development in Zimbabwe	Textual data	Observational	DOC (.doc)	Raw and processed data	No	No	54KB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CesHHAR	D3.5
DG 3.7	Database with findings from transect walks and focus group discussions in South Africa	Categorical and textual data	Observational	DOC (doc)	Raw data	Yes	No	120MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & Wits RHI	D3.5
DG 3.8	Database with findings from transect walks and focus group discussions in Zimbabwe	Categorical and textual data	Observational	DOC (doc)	Raw data	Yes	No	119MB	No	Ethics approval for LSHTM & CesHHAR	D3.5
DG 3.9	Database with characteristics of the EWS users and their thermal exposure when using ClimApp-MCH in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe ¹⁰	Numerical & categorical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	IP agreement with TNO (subcontracted) & s protocol #5 (see Table 5)	D3.4 & D5.3

¹⁰ The server at TNO, the subcontracted party for the development of the ClimApp-MCH, handles the weather and air pollution data requests. The ClimApp-MCH user shares their location (latitude and longitude) with the TNO server, which then sends the required weather and air pollution information. The weather information is fetched from the OpenWeatherMaps. The weather and location data is stored in the User Database, containing local data that is only available to the phone itself. The Profile Screen also uses the database to store the user's profile data. When ClimApp-MCH users agree to submit their data through the app, the heat exposure data and their responses such as thermal perception will be collected. These responses and personal information (age, weight, height, GPS location to connect to local weather forecast, heat acclimatization, etc.) are sensitive.

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 3.10	Database with research questions and answers, plus user details, collected through ClimApp-MCH Research Screen	Categorical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	No DG yet	No	Data sharing agreement between YLUND and DTU & protocol #5 (see Table 5)	D3.4 & D5.3
DG 3.11	Algorithms/scripts of the EWS/ClimApp-MCH for pregnant women, postpartum women, infants and health workers	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking	Flutter code	App code	No	No	Programming is ongoing	Yes, on GitHub once programming is done	IP agreement with TNO (subcontracted)	D3.4
DG 3.12	Thermal modelling and cost modelling techniques to inform selection of the building modification	Numerical & categorical data	Data science methods	X	Raw, processed and published data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable	D2.9
DG 3.13	List of heat-health thresholds	Numerical & textual data	Delphi panel	?	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable	D3.3 & D3.4
DG 3.14	Scripts for CARBOMICA modelling	Numerical & textual data	Design thinking & data science	.py	Raw data	No	No	200KB (est.)	Yes, on GitHub once programming is done	Not applicable	D3.7
DG 3.15	List of indicators from WHO Expert Group	Categorical & textual data	Expert opinions	DOC	Processed and published data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable	D3.2 & D6.4
WP4 - Implement monitoring mechanisms, Early Warning Systems, and adaptation and mitigation interventions in health facilities											

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 4.1	Audio recordings of semi-structured interviews with pregnant women and health workers about socio-demographics, heat exposure, heat impacts and adaptive measures, and the economic burden of heat-related stress (baseline; before use of ClimApp-MCH) in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	2GB (est.)	No	(see protocols #1 & #6 in Table 5)	D4.6 & D4.7
DG 4.2	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG4.1	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp); .txt	Processed data	Yes	No	100 MB (est.)	No	(see protocols #1 & #6 in Table 5)	D4.6 & D4.7
WP5 - Evaluate the surveillance, Early Warning Systems, and health facility adaptive and mitigation actions, including cost-effectiveness											
DG 5.1	Questionnaire about EWS acceptability and usability, and uptake of messages (both by pregnant/postpartum women and by health workers) in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Survey	paper sheet CSV (.csv) .txt	Raw data	Yes	No	5MB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #5 in Table 5)	D5.3
DG 5.2	Spreadsheet with household expenditure data of pregnant and postpartum women in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Survey	paper sheet CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	1MB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.5
DG 5.3	Spreadsheet with time-motion study results (endline) in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	2.5GB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.6

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 5.4	Spreadsheet & unstructured text with results of participant observation of work environment and activities conducted in health facilities (endline) Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	20MB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.6
DG 5.5	Questionnaire about well-being, psychological status, perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, administered by the health workers themselves (endline) in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical & textual data	Survey	delimited text CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	100 kb (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.6
DG 5.6	Spreadsheet with results of urine samples (endline) Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Observational	CSV (.csv)	Raw data	Yes	No	1MB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.5
DG 5.7	Audio recordings of in-depth interviews (endline) Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	MPEG4 (.m4a)	Raw data	Yes	No	1GB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.5
DG 5.8	(NVivo) transcripts and analyses based on audio recordings of DG5.7	Textual & audio-visual data	Observational	NVP (.nvp) .txt	Processed data	Yes	No	100 MB per country (est.)	No	(see protocol #6 in Table 5)	D5.5
DR 5.9	Simulation output with energy performance of cooling interventions in health care facilities	Numerical data	Calculated/simulated	CSV (.csv)	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DG yet	No	Not applicable	D5.9

Ref #	Data object/format	Data content	Mode of data collection	File format	Data lifecycle stage	Personal data	Direct identifier	Data size	Open sharing	Legal & ethical requirement	Deliverable
DG 5.10	Investment modelling of mitigation interventions in Kenya	Numerical data	Data science methods/software (based on CARBOMICA)	.py	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Ethics approval for Wits RHI	D5.9
DG 5.11	Investment modelling of mitigation interventions in South Africa	Numerical data	Data science methods/software (based on CARBOMICA)	.py	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable	D5.9
DG 5.12	Investment modelling of mitigation interventions in Zimbabwe	Numerical data	Data science methods/software (based on CARBOMICA)	.py	Raw and processed data	No	No	No DG yet	Yes	Not applicable	D5.9

2.3 Other research outputs to be collected, generated or reused in the project

Other research outputs of HIGH Horizons (apart from data) include the data analysis scripts, the prediction modelling to assess the heat-health impacts, the software developed for the smartphone application ClimApp-MCH, and the CARBOMICA resource allocation tool for mitigation interventions. The related algorithms, scripts and models are included in table 4.

As far as physical outputs are concerned: specimens such as whole blood, serum, and urine from pregnant women and cord blood are collected in Greece and Cyprus and analysed with the purpose of examining the association of biomarkers related to heat exposure and MNCH outcomes. Urine samples of health workers and pregnant women in South Africa and Zimbabwe won't be collected, only the results of the dipstick test.

3 Ethical and legal issues

3.1 Open access restrictions

Because personal and sensitive data are collected in the HIGH Horizons studies, ethical clearances and legal arrangements are essential before conducting the studies and these have an impact on (open) data sharing as well.

The ethics approvals obtained, and data transfer agreements signed within the HIGH Horizons project are listed below.

Datasets with personal data. Since various HIGH Horizons-generated data are health-related, personal and sensitive, we cannot provide full open access to our datasets. As such, the datasets are not entirely openly available and conditions are attached to access the data (= restricted access). Where possible, we take actions to limit the restrictions, i.e., to have our datasets "as open as possible, as closed as needed", by pseudonymisation or anonymisation of personal data where possible and by agreeing on a limited embargo period (i.e., an embargo period of 5 years after finishing the

project). We will grant access to the 'summary statistics' following analysis of data as appropriate.

Actions to limit the restricted access include the following:

- All individual-level data on women, children, and health workers, using observations, checklists, interview guides, photos, recordings and questionnaires, are anonymized at the point of data collection. An identification number specific to the study is used to distinguish each participant and to each facility.
- Data from focus group discussions and key informant interviews are anonymized (if possible) or pseudonymized. Audio files of focus group discussions or interviews are destroyed; their transcripts are made available.
- Data from the cohorts testing the early warning system in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe and the mother-child cohort recruited for the biomarker study in Greece and Cyprus cannot be anonymized as we need to keep the link between personal and health information during the cohort period. However, we will pseudonymize these data to secure their privacy.

The final decision about how openly accessible the HIGH Horizons datasets will be, will be taken at the end of the project based on the sensitivity of the data, the importance of sharing our data and findings for secondary analyses as well as the quality.

Datasets with personal data are securely stored by HIGH Horizons partners on their local servers, and only anonymised data(sets) are shared internally between HIGH Horizons partners, as well as externally in trusted repositories.

The research teams in Kenya, Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe remain owner of the samples and data they collect. The provider and the processor will be involved in deciding how to restrict future use of the data in collaboration with the Steering Committee.

Non-personal data (e.g. environmental or temperature data) are made openly available where relevant.

De-identified data. HIGH Horizons does not collect direct identifiers such as name, home address. However, we will have indirect identifiers such as date of birth.

GDPR register. Minimal personal data from HIGH Horizons partners and stakeholders are stored securely on the HIGH Horizons SharePoint folder, and are not accessible by external partners. We don't keep a GDPR register for the HIGH Horizons project.

Ethics approvals. Our approach for ethics applications is:

- Prepare a 'mother protocol' (by the lead partner of the study), including procedures to guarantee confidentiality, such as informed consent forms, alignment with the GDPR rules, secure data storage and management of personal data;
- Seek ethical clearance for the 'mother protocol' from the Ethics Committee or Institutional Review Board of the lead partner;
- Modify and align the mother protocol to the requirements of the Ethics Committee or Institutional Review Board in each of the implementing countries;
- Seek ethical clearance for the 'country protocol' from each of the Ethics Committees.

So far, we have received ethical clearance for several study protocols, we are preparing to resubmit two protocols in Sweden¹¹ and we started drafting the protocol for the adaptation interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe. The status of all protocols is given in table 5. When the mother protocol is an approved HIGH Horizons project deliverable, we have deposited it in Zenodo (see protocols #2, 4, and 5b). For protocol #3, we have prepared a study protocol (21) on how HIGH Horizons analyses and

¹¹ We received minor comments on the health worker study protocol submitted in May 2024 to the Swedish Ethics Review Authority, and in August 2024 we plan to resubmit this protocol as well as submit the EWS messaging study protocol.

assesses the population-level heat-health impacts in the countries for which we have a database¹². This study protocol can be used by others to analyse country data they own.

Table 5: Overview of HIGH Horizons protocols and their status

Protocol #	Topic	Lead partner	Greece	Kenya	South Africa	Sweden	Zimbabwe
Protocol #1	#1a. Protocol for pre-intervention assessment of health workers' wellbeing	LSHTM; APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	Re-submission planned in August 2024	APPROVED
	#1b. Protocol for post-intervention assessment of health workers' wellbeing	LSHTM: this study will be included in protocol #6	Not applicable	Not applicable	This study will be included in protocol #6	This study will be included in protocol #6	This study will be included in protocol #6
Protocol #2	Protocol for pre-post study evaluation of mitigation interventions (20)	CeSHHAR; Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable
Protocol #3	Protocol for access to and reuse of birth registry and MNCH data	UNI GRAZ; APPROVED	APPROVED	Data sharing agreement with UGRAZ	APPROVED	Not applicable*	Not applicable
Protocol #4	Protocol for biomarker study (13)	UTH; APPROVED	APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
Protocol #5	#5a. Protocol for co-design of locally-appropriate messages	LSHTM; APPROVED	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	Re-submission planned in august 2024	APPROVED
	#5b. Protocol for design and pilot testing of EWS & evaluation (19)	ULUND: Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	APPROVED	Planned in October 2024	APPROVED

¹² Apart from the country datasets available to HIGH Horizons partners in Greece, Sweden, Kenya and South Africa, a subcontractor from our Swedish partner KI, ASL Roma, has access to a regional dataset in Italy. Its data access and usage are regulated by regional and national laws to which ASL Roma Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service complies.

Protocol #	Topic	Lead partner	Greece	Kenya	South Africa	Sweden	Zimbabwe
Protocol #6	Protocol for co-design of adaptation interventions	LSHTM; Protocol but no application	Not applicable	Not applicable	Protocol but no ethics application	Not applicable	Protocol but no ethics application

Notes: *Sweden has an ethics permission for the dataset covering 2014-2018 but a new submission is planned for expanding the pregnancy-register database 2014-2023. ** HIGH Horizons implementing partner Wits RHI held a joint co-design workshop for the adaptation interventions to be implemented by both HIGH Horizons and the [HAPI study](#). Wits RHI therefore submitted a co-design amendment on the HAPI protocol that included HIGH Horizons, along with an informed consent form that was used during the co-design process.

Data transfer agreements. So far data transfer agreements have been established between:

- UGRAZ and AKHS Kenya for the transfer of the dataset from Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa in Kenya to UGRAZ for heat-health data analysis by UGRAZ;
- Wits RHI and LSHTM for the transfer of the database from the Soweto District in South Africa for heat-health data analysis by LSHTM.

3.2 Valorisation of research

Within HIGH Horizons we do not have data or research materials subject to confidentiality due to valorisation potential. We do not foresee any patent applications.

3.3 Third-party agreements

So far, we do not have any data or research materials affected by third-party agreements.

3.4 Intellectual property

The predictive models based on heat stress indices and human heat balance models, algorithms, and source codes of the ClimApp-MCH are already openly accessible through GitHub. All coding modifications made during the HIGH Horizons project are similarly made available as they are produced. The app is developed in the Open-Source Platform Cordova (Apache Cordova) and built for specific smartphone platforms (e.g., Android). The app is hosted by HIGH Horizons partner ULUND and their subcontractor TNO. The data is saved at another consortium partner DTU. The app is currently owned

by the ClimApp Consortium. For teaching and research ClimApp, it is free, but for commercial use, the ClimApp consortium must agree.

4 Metadata and documentation

4.1 Findable and accessible data

Repositories. For datasets and other research materials HIGH Horizons uses two **repositories**, Zenodo and GitHub:

- HIGH Horizons has created its own community as part of the Zenodo [Open repository for EU-funded research](#), which is set up specifically for research outputs from Horizon Europe: [Search HIGH Horizons \(zenodo.org\)](#); approved project deliverables are deposited in Zenodo in these two communities;
- On GitHub we created our own [HIGH Horizons repository](#), but many researchers also share their datasets or software in their own public repositories.

Metadata. We follow the repository guidelines for the **metadata**, including description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo; Horizon Europe and UKRI funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset or research material, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.

Upon submission in the data repository, we provide search keywords to optimize our data and research materials for reuse. Where possible the same keywords are used in the publications.

We also use Zenodo's harvest module to record metadata in the Zenodo community collection.

Persistent identifiers. HIGH Horizons uses **persistent identifiers** for

- authors: *ORCID ID*
 - We encourage all HIGH Horizons researchers to register with ORCID
- organisations: *ROR ID*
 - Except for Wits Health consortium (and its health research divisions, Wits RHI and Wits Planetary Health Research) and Aga Khan Health services Kenya, all HIGH Horizons consortium partners have a ROR
- grant: *ID grant number*
 - In the metadata we refer to Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101057843 and UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478
 - We also acknowledge funders by adding “HIGH Horizons has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478” to publications or project deliverables
- publications: *DOI* (e.g., peer-reviewed journal article) or *ISBN* (e.g., WHO publications)
 - For most of our research outputs and publications the editor provides the DOI
 - Zenodo also registers DOIs for deposited records and research outputs and therefore we upload HIGH Horizons project deliverables and study protocols on Zenodo
- datasets: *DOI*
 - The dataset of the heat-health glossary is deposited in [GitHub](#) and Zenodo (22)
 - We consider sharing anonymised processed data on Zenodo in the future

- software: *DOI*
 - The codes of [ClimApp](#) and the changes made for the personalised early warning system for pregnant women and health workers, ClimApp-MCH, is shared openly on GitHub by the developers and once the ClimApp-MCH is final we plan to deposit the software in Zenodo to have a DOI for the software
 - The scripts and codes for [CARBOMICA](#), the resource optimisation tool for carbon emission mitigation interventions, are also deposited in GitHub by the developers, and we also consider to deposit them in Zenodo once final.

In Zenodo metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain, so no authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it. For accessing the data in Zenodo the user may need to be registered and require login to the user's account, but this also depend on the level of access chosen by HIGH Horizons (i.e. closed, open, or embargoed access).¹³

In Zenodo, metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it. Data will remain available and findable for 20 years. Metadata will remain available after 20 years.

¹³ [Zenodo](#) (access and reuse)

4.2 Interoperable data

The HIGH Horizons data is mainly processed by the researchers in REDCap¹⁴, ODK¹⁵, Wombat¹⁶, NVivo, MaxQDA, Word and Excel, but data sharing will be in non-proprietary formats (.pdf, .txt, .csv), which are interoperable. The linked metadata make the data partly machine readable. Where possible the formats that are preferred by the repositories (i.e. Zenodo, GitHub) are used.

Standard vocabulary is used, such as country codes and ISO format of date-time. We will use the standard vocabulary used in clinical trials¹⁷ and correct applicable clinical ontologies. In addition, we document all variables throughout the study.

Because HIGH Horizons is situated at the intersection between climate and health sciences, the terminology used by the different disciplines has been inventoried in a glossary for internal use by our own researchers, but also for external purposes (22). No other project-specific ontologies or vocabularies are used.

5 Data storage & security

The handling of the overall data management, the project's SharePoint folders and files, the UGent shared network drive "shares" and repositories on behalf of HIGH Horizons, as well as general data management issues related to the project, are the responsibility of the project coordinator. The storage of confidential and personal information from

¹⁴ REDCap is a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases. The software is not open source but is installed on a local web server, e.g. at the University of Thessaly where it is used for the biomarker study, or at Wits RHI, ULUND and CeSHHAR for collecting data during the EWS implementation and evaluation.

¹⁵ LSHTM uses the ODK platform: [LSHTM ODK Servers - LSHTM Global Health Analytics](#). ODK is an open source electronic data capture tool maintained by a collaborative global community. The LSHTM Global Health Analytics group has set up an ODK service to help scientific researchers use ODK in their projects. This service is available on a pay-what-you-can basis to anyone working at LSHTM, or collaborating with LSHTM researchers on research that can benefit global health. The use of ODK has to be acknowledged in publications: "Electronic data solutions were provided by LSHTM Global Health Analytics (odk.lshtm.ac.uk)."

¹⁶ WOMBAT, Work Observation Method by Activity Timing, is a computerised tool to collect multiple dimensions of clinical work patterns (who, what, when and why) as well as comprehensive contextual information (patients and colleagues) and interrupted tasks.

¹⁷ <https://prsinfo.clinicaltrials.gov/definitions.html>

questionnaires, informed consent forms and urine and blood sample data are managed locally by our partners in Greece, South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe.

Data security is of major importance in the HIGH Horizons project. The protection of personal data is ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies, including:

- Through all steps in data gathering, data entry, data cleaning, and analysis, only HIGH Horizons team members have access to the data. The respective data managers will regularly evaluate that people have access only to the information that they strictly need to have access to.
- The Ghent University SharePoint is used for secure storage at the consortium level. This instance is set up 'on-premise,' meaning that the data are stored within Ghent University. This ensures that the data are protected in case a device is lost or stolen and guarantees better protection in terms of privacy. SharePoint also provides a backup mechanism for versioning.
- Each HIGH Horizons partner stores the data collected on its institutional network, on a secure server protected by two-level authentication.
- Data storage on local devices is avoided at all times. If storing a copy of the data on local machines is inevitable, then the data will be password-protected and only include de-identified data.
- Screens are locked when researchers leave their desks.
- Data are not sent by email but transferred safely using encryption or secure tools like Filesender (and not WeTransfer, Dropbox or Box).
- When working in a non-digital format: physical access to confidential data will be controlled; for example, field notes or a box of confidential interviews (transcripts, field notes) or completed informed consent forms will not be left unattended behind locked doors.
- When the retention period of confidential data has expired, and there are no further obligations or reasons to keep them, this information will be destroyed

safely. This could mean shredding paper before it is disposed of for physical documents. As for digital data, special erasing software will be used.

- The study results may be published for scientific purposes, but anonymity will be protected at all times, and no results will be linked to specific individuals.

6 Data preservation

As project coordinator, Ghent University encourages all HIGH Horizons partners to preserve the relevant research data for a minimum of 5 years¹⁸. Specimens such as whole blood, serum, and urine from pregnant women and cord blood collected by UTH in Greece and Cyprus are stored 30 years after collection, in accordance with the traceability obligations set out in Art.36 of Greek Presidential Decree 26/2008, which transcribes Directive 2004/23/EC into Greek Law.

Data and research materials will be safely stored for long term preservation and curation, because the security standards of the trusted repositories apply. The HIGH Horizons datasets and other research outputs that need to be preserved after the project will be listed in the final DMP.

7 Data sharing and reuse

All the datasets that HIGH Horizons has deposited in online repositories with the purpose of being shared and reused will be listed in the next update of the DMP in August 2025. Data and research materials deposited in the trusted repositories will include README files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.

The Steering Committee will decide on granting access to the data collected and produced after consulting the relevant owners and processors. If granted access, licenses will be given depending on the purpose of the secondary analysis. Embargo periods may apply.

¹⁸ See UGent's RDM policy framework (4): [Preserving data — Ghent University \(ugent.be\)](https://www.ugent.be/en/research-operations/rdm/policy-framework)

After project closure decisions about granting access to the open data and research outputs will be taken by the respective partner organisations.

8 Costs and resources

HIGH Horizons uses repositories free of charge for storing and accessing data. If costs related to data management occur during the HIGH Horizons project, these will be covered by the Horizon Europe grant.

At this stage we do not expect costs for long-term storage and archiving and therefore it is expected that no financial resources are required after project closure.

9 References

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